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19th November 2025

Dr Piotr Osypiński

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Dear Dr Osypiński

Thank you for submitting your sample for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating at the Oxford Luminescence Dating Laboratory, University of Oxford.

Your samples have been dated using the OSL signal from quartz using the single aliquot regenerative protocol and I can confirm the calculated ages below.

Sample Name	OLD Sample Code	Depth (cm)	Equivalent Dose (Gy)	Total Dose Rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)
OSL sample #1	SER1	170	28.48 ± 1.44	4.46 ± 0.24	6.38 ± 0.47
OSL sample #2	SER2	130	19.88 ± 0.33	4.24 ± 0.24	4.68 ± 0.28
OSL sample #3	SER3	110	19.46 ± 0.35	4.01 ± 0.22	4.85 ± 0.28
OSL sample #4	SER4	80	17.91 ± 0.98	4.25 ± 0.23	4.21 ± 0.33
OSL sample #5	SER5	30	13.79 ± 0.30	3.69 ± 0.22	3.73 ± 0.23

Please see the following full dating report for further details relating to your sample. I have also included as an appendix the report of Dr Jim Feathers that you provided me in June 2025 to allow comparison between the two datasets.

Yours faithfully,

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads 'J Durcan'.

Dr Julie Durcan

Researcher, School of Geography and the Environment, University of Oxford
Oxford Luminescence Dating Laboratory Co-ordinator

Dating Report for Samples SER1-5, Loiyangalani 1 Site

Sample Preparation Procedures

Samples for optically stimulated dating were opened and prepared under orange light conditions at the Oxford Luminescence Dating Laboratory, University of Oxford. Standard laboratory treatment is undertaken at the laboratory (e.g. Wintle 1997). For coarse (sand sized) grain samples, sediments are treated with hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide to remove carbonate and organic matter, sieved to isolate a fixed grain size range for dating, and heavy liquid density separation is undertaken to separate heavy mineral, quartz, and potassium feldspar mineral fractions. For feldspar dating, grains are not chemically treated further and for quartz dating hydrofluoric acid is used to remove the alpha-irradiated outer layer of the quartz grains. For fine (silt sized) grain dating, sediments are treated with hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide to remove carbonate and organic matter and settling (using Stokes' Law principles) is used to isolate different grain size fractions. For polymineral dating (feldspar dominant), no further treatment is undertaken. For quartz dating, chemical etching in fluorosilicic acid is undertaken to purify the quartz.

Grain Size Selection

For this set of samples, the intention was to date the coarse grain fraction (sands) using the single grain dating technique. However, all 5 samples yielded low amounts of sand sized grains. When the density separation stage of preparation was undertaken, heavy mineral grains were separated out using sodium polytungstate (SPT) (density 2.70 g. cm^3), however all >99% of remaining grains had densities of less than 2.58 g. cm^3 . Very little mass was retrieved in the range of $2.62 - 2.70 \text{ g. cm}^3$ used to isolate quartz. The SPT stage was repeated three times, the final time to with a new batch of SPT. Samples from other projects treated at the same time separated as expected. Therefore I conclude a lack of coarse grain quartz. The $<2.58 \text{ g.cm}^3$ fraction, which should've have comprised potassium feldspar was tested for dating, but did not produce infrared stimulated luminescence (IRSL) signals characteristic of potassium feldspar. Therefore, dating proceeded using fine grain quartz grains.

When dried, the fine grain (less than $63 \mu\text{m}$) component of all 5 samples contained an unknown dark brown, shiny component which had settled out as the upper layer of sediment (figure 1). I have not seen this material before and do not know what it is. In order to avoid this material which appears to be fine grained in nature, the $38-63 \mu\text{m}$ was selected for fine grain dating.

Figure 1: Photographs of the dark, shiny material which dried out at the surface of all 5 SER samples. Material unknown.

Equivalent Dose

Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) measurements were made using a Risø TL/OSL luminescence reader fitted with a $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source, which had a dose rate of approximately 6 Gy/min. Ultraviolet luminescence signals were stimulated with blue light emitting diodes (470 nm) and detected through a bialkali photo multiplier tube fitted with 7.5 mm U340 filters. The equivalent dose was measured using the single aliquot regenerative dose protocol (SAR; Murray and Wintle, 2000). A pre-heat of 220°C for 10 s and cut-heat of 160°C for 10 s were used following preheat and dose recovery test (figure 2). The suitability of this protocol was assessed using a dose recovery test (figure 3).

Figure 2: Combined pre-heat and dose recovery ratio test results. The natural signals from 9 aliquots of sample SER2 were bleached and a known dose beta dose of ~ 26 Gy was administered. The samples were then measured using the SAR protocol to assess the suitability of pre-heating at 200°C, 220°C, and 240°C. For all 9 samples, the dose recovery ratio (the administered divided by the measured dose) is close to unity, indicating that temperatures across the 200 – 240°C range are suitable for use in the SAR dating protocol. A pre-heat temperature of 220°C was selected because results were the least dispersed at this temperature.

Figure 3: Dose recovery test results. To test the suitability of the SAR protocol, a dose recovery test on SER2 was undertaken using the same measurement protocol as the combined pre-heat dose recovery test. The dose recovery ratio for each of the 9 aliquots was within $\pm 5\%$ of unity, with an average dose recovery ratio of 0.99 ± 0.02 . This result indicates the SAR protocol is suitable for the measurement of this sample. Dose recovery tests on the other four samples yielded similar ratios.

In total, 18 aliquots of fine grain quartz were measured to establish the equivalent dose for each sample. The equivalent doses were calculated from signal from the first 0.1 s of stimulation and a background averaged over the final 10 s of measurement was subtracted. All OSL signals were screened with standard rejection criteria: 1) test dose signal $>3\sigma$ of background levels, 2) recuperations $<5\%$, 3) recycling ratios and 4) OSL IR depletion ratios within 10% of unity. All measured signals satisfied these criteria and were included in age calculation.

Optically stimulated luminescence signals measured from this sample had high sensitivity and decay curves which reduced rapidly to background levels with a few seconds of light stimulation indicative of the dominance of the fast component (figure 4). All measured signals satisfied the rejection criteria listed above and are considered suitable for dating. Table 1 summarises the overdispersion, a measure of the spread in the underlying equivalent dose population and the equivalent dose (D_e) calculated with the central age model (CAM) of Galbraith et al. (1999). D_e values are in the range of 13.8 – 28.5 Gy, which are well within the saturation limits of the quartz OSL signal (e.g. Durcan and Duller, 2024) and individual D_e values were checked to make sure they were not saturated. The overdispersion values vary between 6.7 and 22.9%, indicating that there is some spread in the measured D_e values, particularly for samples SER1 and SER4. This is visible in the kernel density estimate plots (figure 5) for each sample. For these samples in particular, high and low D_e values are evident. The underlying overdispersion (or spread) of the D_e distribution is likely to be higher and is potentially masked here by signal averaging due to the fine grain nature of the sediments dated. That said, within each of the dose distributions, a large proportion of individual D_e values are consistent with a central value. Future dating work would benefit from dating the sand sized component of the samples. This was the original intention in this study, however the samples did not contain sufficient sand for dating, and of the sand-sized grains retrieved, the amount of quartz found was extremely limited and the feldspar component did not yield luminescence signals characteristic of potassium feldspar.

Figure 4: Example OSL decay curve (Sample SER1)

Table 1: Equivalent dose summary. 18 aliquots of each sample was used for D_e calculation.

Sample	Overdispersion (%)	CAM D_e (Gy)
SER1	21.05 ± 3.63	28.48 ± 1.44
SER2	6.67 ± 1.29	19.88 ± 0.33
SER3	6.87 ± 1.39	19.46 ± 0.35
SER4	22.89 ± 3.94	17.91 ± 0.98
SER5	8.73 ± 1.67	13.79 ± 0.30

De distribution - SER1

De distribution - SER2

Figure 5: Kernel density estimate plots for samples SER1-5. Individual D_e values and uncertainties are shown in ascending order, with the box plot showing distribution parameters: median bold line, box delimited by the first and third quartile, whiskers defined by the extremes and outliers shown as points.

Environmental Dose Rate

Concentrations of Uranium, Thorium, and Potassium were measured using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry at the School of Geography and the Environment, University of Oxford. There was broad intra-sample agreement in the concentrations of these radionuclides, although duplicate measurements were made on samples SER 2 and 5 given the slightly lower concentrations of Uranium. Radionuclide concentrations were converted to infinite matrix dose rates using the conversion factors of Guerin et al. (2012). Dose rates were adjusted for attenuation by grain size (Guerin et al., 2012), chemical etching (Bell, 1979), an a -value of 0.038 ± 0.004 (Rees-Jones, 1995) and moisture content of $35 \pm 5\%$. The cosmic dose rate was calculated mathematically using the geographic location and position within the sediment matrix of the sample using the equations of Prescott and Hutton (1994). The total environmental dose rate is comprised of the alpha, beta, gamma and cosmic environmental dose rates, and all calculations were made in DRAC v1.2 (Durcan et al., 2015). The overall environmental dose rates for the 5 samples vary between 3.7 and 4.5 Gy/ka.

Table 2: Dose rate (\dot{D}) data summary. Uncertainties of $\pm 10\%$ were attributed to the Uranium (U), Thorium (Th) and Potassium (K) concentrations. A water content of $35 \pm 5\%$ was used and further attenuation factors are detailed in the text. Dose rates were calculated in DRAC v1.2 (Durcan et al., 2015). Calculations were made prior to rounding and values are reported to 2 decimal places.

Sample	Depth (cm)	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	K (%)	Alpha \dot{D} (Gy/ka)	Beta \dot{D} (Gy/ka)	Gamma \dot{D} (Gy/ka)	Cosmic \dot{D} (Gy/ka)	Total \dot{D} (Gy/ka)
SER1	170	4.01	23.07	2.84	0.23 ± 0.05	2.40 ± 0.20	1.63 ± 0.12	0.12 ± 0.02	4.46 ± 0.24
SER2	130	2.61	20.65	3.09	0.19 ± 0.04	2.37 ± 0.21	1.48 ± 0.11	0.21 ± 0.02	4.24 ± 0.24
SER3	110	4.08	17.05	2.68	0.20 ± 0.04	2.21 ± 0.19	1.40 ± 0.10	0.21 ± 0.02	4.01 ± 0.22
SER4	80	4.91	15.49	2.90	0.20 ± 0.04	2.38 ± 0.20	1.45 ± 0.10	0.22 ± 0.02	4.25 ± 0.23
SER5	30	1.24	17.38	2.89	0.14 ± 0.03	2.07 ± 0.19	1.22 ± 0.10	0.27 ± 0.03	3.69 ± 0.22

Age Calculation

For OSL dating, the age is calculated by dividing the equivalent dose by the environmental dose rate. Final ages (in thousands of year, ka) are shown in table 3. Ages date to the mid-Holocene, ranging from 3.73 ± 0.23 ka at the top of the sequence to 6.38 ± 0.47 ka for the deepest sample (SER1, depth 170 cm). The uncertainty (at 1 sigma) varies between 6-8% for the five samples. The OSL ages presented here have been calculated using the quartz OSL signal from fine grained sediments. Pre-heat and dose recovery tests indicate that the measurement protocol used can successfully recover a laboratory administered dose. The signals observed from these samples in the laboratory are characteristic of quartz luminescence signals, with thermoluminescence curves showing the characteristic 110°C peak and OSL signals decaying rapidly and near-exponentially to background levels within a couple of seconds of exposure to light. Ages have been calculated using the central age model (CAM). Dose distributions show most individual D_e values are consistent with a central value, and for this reason, as well as the signals being derived from fine sediment grains, CAM (statistically very similar to a weight mean) was used for age calculation. The overdispersion values

presented do show some spread in the D_e data, despite the fine grain signals used for dating. This suggests that there is underlying spread in D_e , however this cannot be tested further in the absence of coarse grains available for dating.

Table 3: Age summary.

Sample	Depth (cm)	Equivalent Dose (Gy)	Total Dose Rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)
SER1	170	28.48 ± 1.44	4.46 ± 0.24	6.38 ± 0.47
SER2	130	19.88 ± 0.33	4.24 ± 0.24	4.68 ± 0.28
SER3	110	19.46 ± 0.35	4.01 ± 0.22	4.85 ± 0.28
SER4	80	17.91 ± 0.98	4.25 ± 0.23	4.21 ± 0.33
SER5	30	13.79 ± 0.30	3.69 ± 0.22	3.73 ± 0.23

Further Investigation of OSL Signals

From a luminescence perspective, the calculation OSL ages appear robust. Quartz OSL signals decay rapidly and near-exponentially to background levels within a couple of seconds of stimulation, which is characteristic of a fast component dominated signal. The combined pre-heat and dose recovery and dose recovery test results demonstrate that the applied SAR protocol is capable of recording a laboratory administered, known dose. There is some overdispersion observed within the equivalent dose distributions, even at fine-grain scales of analyses, and this would benefit from further investigation if coarse grain dating were an option. Radionuclide concentrations are internally consistent within the sequence for the most part and concentrations are in line with those measured by Dr Jim Feathers (University of Washington) and reported in a previous dating report provided by Dr Piotr Osypiński.

However, Dr Osypiński was expecting the samples to date to the late Pleistocene rather than the mid-Holocene ages calculated from these samples. Given that the dose rates calculated are inline with those calculated in a previous study (table 4 and appendix), therefore if there were to be an issue with these ages, it is hypothesised this would lay in the equivalent doses.

Table 4: Radionuclide concentration summary for samples UW1071 and UW1072 collected from the Loiyangalani site. Data from report by Jim Feathers, included as appendix below.

Sample	²³⁸ U (ppm)	²³² Th (ppm)	K (%)
UW1071	3.24 ± 0.34	26.08 ± 2.33	3.02 ± 0.04
UW1072	3.69 ± 0.31	20.25 ± 1.86	2.92 ± 0.18

To verify the quartz OSL equivalent doses, 2 discs of the polymineral (PM) fine grain sediment were measured. A post-infra infrared (pIRIR) protocol was used for dating (following Smedley et al., 2019) and the pIRIR₂₂₅ signal was targeted because this signal is generally found to be athermally stable (ibid.). 2 PM discs were measured to facilitate comparison with the quartz OSL

data (table 5). The environmental dose rate for the PM samples is slightly higher than the quartz because an internal potassium dose rate is calculated for the PM samples. Accordingly equivalent doses can be expected to be higher. In table 5, the ages calculated for both the PM and quartz components of the SER1-5 samples date to the Holocene and can be considered consistent. That the two signals provide consistent age estimates provides more confidence in the calculated OSL ages.

To provide an additional check of the quartz OSL signals, the thermoluminescence (TL) signal up to 450°C (heating rate of 5°C/s) was measured following a 50 Gy dose, as was the linearly modulated (LM-) OSL signal from the same dose (LM-OSL measured at 125°C following a pre-heat of 220°C for 10 s). For all 5 samples, all signals show characteristic properties of quartz OSL, notably the 110°C TL curve and the de-trapping of the fast component after ~10-20 s of LM stimulation. Example curves are provided in figures 6 and 7. These signals suggest that the OSL signal originates from quartz. Data from the final signal check is shown in figure 7. To check signal stability, sensitivity corrected luminescence was measured and calculated across 6 measurement cycles using a 100 Gy dose. Measurements were made without delay for cycles 1-3 and 4-6. However a 100 hour pause was introduced between cycle 3 and 4. In the instance of any signal decay, this pause would provide sufficient time for a reduction in the OSL signal prior to measurement of cycle 4. In the case of signal instability therefore, a reduction in the sensitivity corrected luminescence at cycle 4 would be expected and could be further investigated. Figure 8 shows the luminescence data for all 6 cycles for sample SER1, with all sensitivity corrected luminescence measurements agreeing within uncertainty. These tests were conducted for all 5 samples with consistent results. It is therefore concluded that there is no evidence for signal instability and further testing is not required.

Table 5: Fine grain quartz (Q) OSL and polymineral (PM) pIR-IRSL comparison. For quartz OSL ages, 18 aliquots were used for equivalent dose calculation, for the PM pIR-IRSL ages, only 2 aliquots were measured. The PM data is not intended or suitable for age calculation or interpretation purposes. Instead this data facilitates a rapid check of the quartz data.

Sample	Equivalent Dose (Gy)		Total Dose Rate (Gy/ka)		Age (ka)	
	Q	PM	Q	PM	Q	PM
SER1	28.48 ± 1.44	37.89 ± 4.50	4.46 ± 0.24	4.91 ± 0.26	6.38 ± 0.47	7.72 ± 1.00
SER2	19.88 ± 0.33	19.88 ± 0.33	4.24 ± 0.24	4.64 ± 0.26	4.68 ± 0.28	4.77 ± 0.29
SER3	19.46 ± 0.35	19.46 ± 0.35	4.01 ± 0.22	4.41 ± 0.24	4.85 ± 0.28	5.33 ± 0.29
SER4	17.91 ± 0.98	17.91 ± 0.98	4.25 ± 0.23	4.66 ± 0.25	4.21 ± 0.33	4.77 ± 0.29
SER5	13.79 ± 0.30	13.79 ± 0.30	3.69 ± 0.22	4.02 ± 0.23	3.73 ± 0.23	4.77 ± 0.32

Figure 6: Example thermoluminescence (TL) curves from one aliquot of each of the SER samples. The 110°C TL peak characteristic of quartz luminescence is evident in all 5 curves

Figure 7: Linearly-modulated (LM-) OSL signals.

Figure 8: OSL signal stability assessment. Sensitivity corrected luminescence was measured across 6 measurement cycles. There were no delays between measurement cycles 1-3 and 4-6, however there was a 100 hour pause between the measurement of cycle 3 and 4. In the event of OSL signal loss due to signal stability issues, an obvious decrease in the sensitivity corrected luminescence of cycle 4 would be expected.

References

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APPENDIX

**OSL DATING OF LOIYANGALANI RIVER VALLEY SEDIMENTS, SERENGETI
NATIONAL PARK, TANZANIA**

By James K. Feathers and Christina J. Fusch, University of Washington

Provided by Piotr Osypiński on 26/06/2025

OSL DATING OF LOIYANGALANI RIVER VALLEY SEDIMENTS, SERENGETI NATIONAL PARK, TANZANIA

21 February 2005

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Two sediment samples were collected for luminescence dating from alluvial sediments associated with archaeological remains in the Loiyangalani River valley in Serengeti National Park, Tanzania. The samples were submitted by John R. F. Bower of Serengeti Genesis. The site from which the samples were obtained has been designated HcJd1. Table 1 gives the laboratory numbers, provenience and burial depth of the samples. Two radiocarbon dates obtained from unit 2 range in age from 10-14 ka.

Table 1

<i>Laboratory #</i>	<i>Sample #</i>	<i>Stratigraphic unit</i>	<i>Burial depth</i>
UW1071	OSL#1	Unit 2 (TP 13 N wall)	0.85 m
UW1072	OSL#2	Unit 1 (TP13 N wall)	1.19 m

Radioactivity was measured by thick source alpha counting, flame photometry (for K contents) and beta counting. *In situ* CaSO₄: Dy dosimeters were also emplaced. Measurements from the dosimeters are still underway, so results here are only based on the laboratory measurements. Table 2 gives the radioactive concentrations from alpha counting and flame photometry (and assuming secular equilibrium). Also given are the beta dose rates, comparing those measured directly from beta counting with those calculated from the alpha counting and flame photometry. The beta counting results are slightly higher but not significantly so. Such agreement suggests that any possible disequilibrium in the U and Th decay chains is not significant. The alpha counting/flame photometry results were the ones used in age calculation. Moisture contents listed reflect moisture conditions at the time of sample collection. Large error terms are included to account for changes through time.

Table 2

<i>Sample</i>	²³⁸ U (ppm)	²³² Th (ppm)	K (%)	<i>Beta dose rates (Gy/ka)</i>		<i>Moisture</i> (%)
				Beta- counting	Alpha-counting/ Flame photometer	
UW1071	3.24±0.34	26.08±2.33	3.022±0.035	3.61±0.08	3.44±0.25	37±10
UW1072	3.69±0.31	20.25±1.86	2.922±0.180	3.44±0.16	3.18±0.24	35±10

Equivalent dose was determined on both polymineral fine grains and on 90-180µm quartz. All fractions were treated with HCl and H₂O₂ to remove carbonates and reduce organics. Wet sieving was employed to separate grains smaller and larger than 90µm. Microscopic examination showed that grains > 90µm were single grains and not conglomerates. Fine grains (4-11µm) were isolated by settling a portion of the <90µm fraction in acetone for two and 20 minutes and then evaporating onto stainless steel discs. Analysis was performed on two coarse grained fractions: 90-125µm and 125-180µm. These were isolated by dry sieving. They were etched for 40 minutes in 48% HF and density separated using a polysodium tungstate solution of 2.68 specific gravity, saving the light (quartz) fraction.

Equivalent dose was measured using the single aliquot regenerative (SAR) method (Murray and Wintle 2000). The fine-grain measurements used the so-called double SAR method, which includes an infrared exposure (at both 125°C and 200°C) prior to a blue light exposure. SAR was applied to single grains for the coarse grains. Some doses were preceded by an IRSL exposure to identify feldspar contaminants. Table 3 gives the SAR protocol used.

Table 3

<i>Sequence for Coarse-grain SAR</i>	<i>Sequence for Fine-grain SAR</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dose (D_i) 2. Preheat: 240°C 10 sec 3. OSL (540nm, 1s at 125°C) 4. Test dose (4.35 Gy) 5. Preheat: 160°C 1 sec 6. OSL (540nm, 1s at 125°C) 7. repeat steps 1-6 for each D_i 8. Dose (D_j) 9. IRSL (880nm, 40s at 125°C) 10. repeat steps 2-4 11. IRSL (880nm, 40s at 125°C) 12. repeat steps 5-6 13. repeat steps 8-12 for each D_j 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dose (D_i) 2. Preheat: 240°C 10 sec 3. IRSL (880nm, 100s at 125°C) 4. IRSL (880nm, 300s at 200°C) 5. OSL (470nm, 100s at 125°C) 6. Test dose (3.6Gy) 7. Preheat: 160°C 1 sec 8. repeat steps 3-5 9. repeat steps 1-8 for each D_i
$i = 0$ (natural), 58, 29, 87, 116, 145, 0, 58 Gy for UW1071 $i = 0$ (natural), 14.5, 72.5, 217.5, 290, 362.5, 0, 145 Gy for UW1072 $j = 43.5, 72.5$ Gy for UW1071 $j = 108.75, 181.25$ Gy for UW1072	$i = 0$ (natural), 48, 24, 72, 96, 120, 0, 48 Gy for UW1071 $i = 0$ (natural), 120, 240, 360, 480, 600, 0, 120 Gy for UW1072

These are mainly fine-grained sediments, so the amount of quartz was low. Only about 100 grains from each size fraction (90-125 μ m and 125-180 μ m) were obtained and less than half of these yielded usable signals. Grains were eliminated if they had poor signals (error on test dose higher than 20% or natural signal less than 3 σ above standard deviation of the background), if the natural signal did not intersect the regeneration growth curve (because the growth curve saturated below the level of the natural signal), if they failed the recycle test (violating the assumptions of the SAR method), if they resulted in an equivalent dose not significantly different from zero, or if they were deemed dominated by a feldspar signal. Table 4 shows the number of measured and accepted grains.

Equivalent dose distributions among aliquots were analyzed using the common-age, central-age, and minimum-age models (Galbraith et al. 1999). Common age is like a weighted average except that log values are used. Central age is similar to common age except that it assumes not one true value but a distribution of values. This recognizes the probability that equivalent dose values from single grains will form a distribution, even if all the same age, because of heterogeneity in the dose rates at the scale of single grains and other possible variations in luminescence properties from grain to grain. The central age model also calculates an over-dispersion value indicating a spread of values beyond what might be expected statistically. Among single-grains, over-dispersion values above 20% suggest possible mixing or differential bleaching. Differential bleaching, i.e., some grains being fully bleached (set to zero) at deposition and others only partially bleached, is often a problem with fluvial sediments. In this case, the minimum-age model, which computes the equivalent dose of the youngest grains, is applied. The minimum-age model isolates those grains that statistically could form a single-aged population.

Table 4

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Grain size(μm)</i>	<i>Grains measured</i>	Grains accepted
UW1071	90-125	85	45
	125-180	90	44
UW1072	90-125	100	37
	125-180	99	30

Fine-grain results – Fifteen discs were measured for each sample. Equivalent dose from both IRSL and OSL were derived for each disc. Inter-aliquot differences were small enough that no over-dispersion was calculated for either IRSL or OSL on UW1071 or for IRSL on UW1072. For OSL on UW1072 the over-dispersion was only 7.7 percent. The common age model was used to determine equivalent dose. Table 5 shows the IRSL equivalent dose values to be significantly smaller than those for OSL. This can be attributed to anomalous fading. A fading test was conducted using the double SAR protocol but keeping the regeneration dose the same and inserting different times between the doses and OSL measurements. Figures 1 and 2 plot IRSL and OSL against the storage time. Descending plots indicate the presence of fading. Fading is evident for most of the IRSL signals, but the OSL results are scattered and of poor precision. Fading is evident for some OSL signals (such as disc 1 for UW1072), but it is difficult to tell on most because of the low precision. An attempt to correct for fading using the Huntley-Lamothe method (2000) did not yield reliable results. It is assumed the OSL result will produce a more accurate age than the IRSL result, but the OSL may still be underestimated. For alpha efficiency corrections, the b-value method was employed, comparing growth curves using beta and alpha irradiations on multi-aliquots (Aitken 1985). The b-value for UW1071 was determined to be $0.841 \pm 0.237 \text{ Gy } \mu\text{m}^2$. A reasonable value could not be obtained from the data collected for UW1072, so a similar value was assumed.

Table 5

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Equivalent dose (Gy)</i>	
	IRSL	OSL
UW1071	49.2 \pm 1.6	56.8 \pm 3.6
UW1072	189 \pm 5	355 \pm 24

Coarse-grain results – The 90-125 μm and 125-180 μm fractions were measured separately. The central age value for both fractions was statistically identical for UW1072, but differed for UW1071. However, Figure 3 shows that the overlap between the two fractions for UW1071 was substantial and that most values were consistent with a common value. The two fractions were combined for all subsequent analyses. (Radial graphs, such as Figure 3, plot some measure of precision against a standardized value of the equivalent dose. The latter is standardized in terms of the number of standard errors away from some reference point. The shaded area encompasses all points within two standard errors of the reference. A straight line drawn from the origin will intersect points of the same value, but different precision, and will intersect the scale on the right at the true equivalent dose for those points.)

The distribution of equivalent dose values for UW1072 is surprisingly tight. Only a few points fell outside the two-standard-error range and an over-dispersion value of zero was obtained (Figure 4). Equivalent dose from the central age model did not differ from that of the common age model. This reflects a well-bleached, unmixed sample. The distribution for UW1071 is somewhat more scattered (Figure 5), and the over-dispersion value is $26.8 \pm 3.8 \%$. This is somewhat higher than what is expected for a well-bleached, unmixed sample. For fluvial sediments, it has been recommended that the minimum age model be employed for over-dispersion values greater than 20% (Olley et al. 2004). Figure 5 shows the distribution around both the central age and minimum age model value. Table 6 gives the equivalent dose values for both samples.

Table 6

Sample	Equivalent dose (Gy)	
	Central-age	Minimum-age
UW1071	47.7±1.9	34.0±3.0
UW1072	258±7	

Ages – Table 7 gives the ages derived in various ways for both samples. The agreement between the fine grain and quartz fractions for UW1072 is clear. This seems to be a well-bleached, unmixed sample. It also suggests that anomalous fading for the fine grained OSL is not significant. This same conclusion about fading can be drawn from the agreement in fine grain and quartz central age values for UW1071. However, for UW1071 the distribution of equivalent dose values suggests a possible problem with mixing or partial bleaching. (The fine-grain result, being an average of many grains, provides no information on this.) It is possible that the over-dispersion reflects mixing with as many grains moving up as moving down in the sediment column, in which case the central age value of equivalent dose would be most appropriate. The agreement with the radiocarbon dates suggests this may be the case.

Table 7

Sample	Age (ka)		
	Fine grain OSL	Quartz central age	Quartz minimum age
UW1071	10.8±0.9	11.8±1.0	8.5±1.0
UW1072	70.7±6.2	68.3±5.1	

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4 – UW1072 single grains

Figure 5 – UW1071 single grains. Blue:center age, yellow:minimum age.